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Determination of Effects of Ethanol Bark Extract of Mahogany (*Sweitenia macrophylla*) on Haematological Parameters of Commercial Cockerels Challenged with Kudu 113 Newcastle Disease Virus Strain

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Newcastle disease (ND) is a viral disease that affects large number of Avian species. This study aimed at determining the effects of ethanol bark extract of mahogany (*Sweitenia macrophylla*) on hematological parameters of cockerels experimentally infected with Kudu 113 strain of Newcastle Disease Virus (vNDVirus). Ethanol bark extraction of *Sweitenia macrophylla* was carried out after which phytochemical constituents were determined. Its safety on chickens was also determined. One hundred and fifty (150) four weeks old cockerels were used for the study which were randomly grouped into 5 constituting of A (negative control given normal feed and water), B (positive control given only the extract), C (given normal feed and water and challenged with the virus), D (given the extract after challenge) and E (given the extract before challenge). The extract was found to contain secondary metabolites like Alkaloids, Glycosides, Tannins, Saponnins, Terpenoids and Phenols. It had a wide safety of margin. There was decrease in packed cell volume, erythrocyte count and hemoglobin in all the groups challenged with NDV. PCV, Hb and Heterophils were highest in the prophylaxis treatment group compared to other infected groups while Lymphocytes were highest in the therapeutic treatment group compared to other infected groups. It was concluded that, administration of *Sweitenia macrophylla* ethanol bark extract for prophylactic and therapeutic treatments at 3000mg/kg enhanced white blood cells production in cockerels experimentally infected with velogenic Newcastle disease virus and. The extract is recommended for prophylaxis administration against Newcastle disease at 3000-5500mg/kg.

Key words: Cockerels; Haematological parameters: Kudu 113 strain; Newcastle disease virus; *Sweitenia macrophylla*

INTRODUCTION

Poultry industry is an essential subsector of agriculture in Nigeria that provides food, employment and other economic resources for the country (Ezekiel *et al.*, 2012). This sector plays a key role in economic development in

Sub-Saharan Africa; and Nigeria specifically (Mengesha, 2011). Systems of poultry production include Extensive, Semi-intensive, and intensive systems. Small-scale poultry production is commonly practiced in the rural communities. The traditional system practices raising of local chicken, the exotic breeds commonly known as the commercial chickens have stimulated an industrial advancement of the poultry raising through specialization

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as egg or meat type strains to satisfy the increasing demand for poultry commodity in the food market (Rekwot *et al.*, 2015).

Newcastle disease (ND) also known as Renikhet disease, Pseudo-fowl plaque or Pseudoencephalitis, is an acute infectious viral disease that can affect large number of poultry (Raw *et al.*, 2009). It is caused by virus in the family of paramyxoviruses. The disease appears in three forms: lentogenic or mild, mesogenic or moderate and velogenic or very virulent forms. The lentogenic strains are very widespread, but cause few disease outbreaks. It usually presents as a respiratory disease, but depression, nervous manifestation or diarrhea may be the prominent clinical form (Absalon *et al.*, 2019). Since the emergence of ND in 1926, there has been continuous emergence of new virulent strains making it an enzootic disease (Snoeck, *et al.*, 2013). The chicken remains the most susceptible to ND (Aliyu *et al.*, 2015). The clinical signs vary widely and are dependent on factors such as: the strain of the virus, species of bird affected, the age of the host (young birds are most susceptible), concurrent infection with other organisms, environmental stress and immune status. Mortality is variable but can be as high as 100 %. Types include viscerotropic, neurotropic, mesogenic, respiratory, and asymptomatic depending on systems affected and severity (Sarcheshmei *et al.*, 2016).

Ethnoveterinary medicine (which involves the use of Probiotics, prebiotics, herbs, and phytochemical products/extracts) has gained interest as potential alternative to the use of conventional medicines in poultry. It has been employed successfully by local communities over decades and is still on the practice (Rates, 2001). The biologically active components of some of these medicinal products possess several therapeutic properties such as antiviral, anticancer, hepatoprotective and immunopotentiating properties (Reis *et al.*, 2017). Mahogany tree (*Sweitenia macrophylla*) has been reported to contain metabolites such as: Tannins, alkaloids, terpenoids, saponins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, phenols, catechin, vitamins, and carbohydrate making it a potential antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, antiparasitic, antitumour, antidiabetic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antipyretic. It has also been found to lower blood pressure (Brookes, 1996).

The antibody titre that is protective against Newcastle disease is 1:32 (Oberländer *et al.*, 2020). Haematological parameters such as Packed cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin, red blood cells (RBCs), white blood cells (WBC) and related indices are commonly examined to assess physiological and pathological changes induced by toxic stress in organism (Manoharam *et al.*, 2021). Hematological parameters are also used as indicators of nutritional status of an animal (Jiwuba *et al.*, 2016). These parameters have been used in the diagnosis of physiological alterations and for determining structural

changes in organs or systems produced by disease and or exposure to toxins (Walencik and Witeska, 2007). The range of normal PCV of chickens is 22-35%, RBC $2.5-3.5 \times 10^6 \mu\text{l}$, Hb 7-13 g/dl, WBC $12-30 \times 10^3$. Lymphocytes 48.33-61.33%, Monocytes 2.00-3.67%, Eosinophils 1.67-5.00%, Basophils 0.00-1.00, Heterophils 40-75% (Bounous, and Stedman, 2000).

There is paucity of literature on the use of bark of Mahogany in the management of Newcastle disease which necessitated this research work. The work aimed at determining the effect of ethanol bark extract of Mahogany (*S. macrophylla*) on haematological parameters of commercial (exotic) cockerels challenged with Kudu 113 NDV strain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study site was poultry pen City Campus, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Sokoto state is located in the extreme North-western part of Nigeria between latitude 13.0533° N and longitude 5.3223° E. The State has an estimated population of more than 6.3 million people as of 2022. The predominant tribes are the Hausa/Fulani who are mostly Muslims. Sokoto Metropolis covers part of Wamakko, Kware, Sokoto North and Sokoto South. Sokoto falls within the Sudan Savannah Ecological Zone (SSMANR, 2007).

Study design

Bark of Mahogany (*Sweitenia macrophylla*) was obtained and ethanol extraction of the bark was carried out. Its phytochemical constituents as well as its safety were determined. One hundred and fifty (150) day old commercial cockerels were obtained and were randomly distributed into five experimental groups (A, B, C, D and E) of 30 chicks each before the commencement of the experiment at 4 weeks of age. They were given normal feed and water. The experimental groups included:

1. Group A: No treatment (negative control).
2. Group B: Given only the extract at four weeks for a period of seven days (positive control).
3. Group C: Only challenged with Kudu 113 velogenic strain of Newcastle Disease Virus at four weeks (positive control).
4. Group D: Given the extract after challenge with the virus at four weeks (therapeutic treatment group).
5. Group E: Given the extract 2 days before challenge with the virus at four weeks (prophylactic treatment group).

Antibody titres of the cockerels were evaluated at four

weeks of age before the experimental infection. Hematological parameters were evaluated to determine the effects of the extract. Twelve separate cockerels were used for determination of safety of the extract.

Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance and approval were sought and obtained from Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC), Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto with reference number UDUS/IACUC/2024/R05.

Collection, preparation and ethanol extraction of *Sweitenia macrophylla* bark

Sweitenia macrophylla tree was identified and the bark was collected in the premises of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria. It was authenticated at Botany Department of Faculty of Biological Science Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria with reference number UDUH/ANS/0123. Extraction of *S. macrophylla* bark was done using ethanol at the Toxicology Laboratory, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto according to Falah *et al.* (2008).

Phytochemical analysis of ethanol bark extract of *S. macrophylla*

Phytochemical constituents of the extract were determined according to procedure described by Edeoga *et al.*, (2005).

Determination of Safety of *S. macrophylla* Bark Extract

Acute oral toxicity of the extract in cockerels used for this research was determined according to OECD (2008).

The Challenge Virus

Inoculum of Kudu 113 strain of Newcastle disease virus was obtained from National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI) Vom, Plateau State, Nigeria. An ampule of the viral content was reconstituted with 10ml of phosphate buffered saline (1:10) following guidelines from the Regional Laboratory for Avian influenza and other transboundary animal diseases. LD₅₀ titer of the virus was 10^{8.5} per ml with storage temperature of 20⁰C±4⁰C.

Birds Sourcing, Grouping and Experimental Infection

A total of 150 apparently healthy day old commercial cockerels were procured from Ibadan, Nigeria for the study and housed in poultry house of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. The chicks were then evaluated by physical

examination for presence of any abnormality or disease. They were raised for four weeks during which brooding was two weeks before commencement of the experiment. They were given commercial chick feed *ad libitum* and provided with clean drinking water and randomly divided into 5 groups each containing thirty birds (Groups A, B, C, D and E). Groups C, D and E were experimentally infected.

Group C: Inoculated with 0.1ml of the diluted virus intraocular at four weeks.

Group D: Inoculated with 0.1ml of the diluted virus intraocular at four weeks and given the extract for five days when signs of ND started manifesting.

Group E: Given the plant extract at 3 weeks 5 days for two days and then Inoculated with 0.1ml of the diluted virus intraocular at four weeks.

Safety Handling Procedures and Biosecurity Measures

Safety measures were taken to avoid contamination with, and spread of the virus to the un-infected control groups through wearing of protective clothing (hand gloves, laboratory coats and boots) during experimental infection and feed and water administration, restriction of visitors and provision of foot dip. Biosecurity was ensured to prevent any incident of infectious diseases in the poultry house.

Blood Collection

About one mL of blood was collected from representative of each group at days 1, 3, 5 and 7 through the wing vein and put in anticoagulant bottle containing Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA), for determination of packed cell volume and differential blood counts, and also put in plain bottles for extraction of sera for hemagglutination test. They were then transported to hematology laboratory of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine in a container with ice packs for analyses.

Evaluation of Antibody Titer Against Newcastle Disease Virus Through Haemagglutination Test

The antibody titer against Newcastle disease virus was determined through Haemagglutination test at four weeks of age in groups C, D and E according to procedure described by Killian (2014).

Determination of Hematological Parameters Among the Groups

Blood samples collected were used to determine the blood profiles of the birds which included Packed Cell Volume (PCV) using the Micro haematocrit method as described by Smith (2022), Hemoglobin concentration (Hb) was determined by the cyanomethemoglobin

Table 1: Mean and Standard error mean (\pm SEM) of hematological parameters of group A cockerels at day 1, 3, 5, and 7

Haematological parameters	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
PCV (%)	27.60 \pm 0.15	27.00 \pm 0.26	27.00 \pm 0.01	27.50 \pm 0.46
Hb (g/dl)	9.20 \pm 0.26	8.52 \pm 0.35	8.92 \pm 0.99	8.89 \pm 0.01
RBC $\times 10^6$ cell/mm ³	2.88 \pm 0.57	2.56 \pm 0.00	2.88 \pm 0.57	2.85 \pm 0.54
WBC \times cell/mm ³	13.17 \pm 0.36	13.43 \pm 0.24	13.25 \pm 0.03	13.45 \pm 0.42
Heterophils (%)	26.33 \pm 0.01	25.67 \pm 0.14	25.5 \pm 0.13	25.89 \pm 0.32
Lymphocytes(%)	70.67 \pm 0.40	71.00 \pm 0.42	72.50 \pm 0.31	71.50 \pm 0.51
Monocytes (%)	2.00 \pm 0.00	2.00 \pm 0.00	2.00 \pm 0.00	2.00 \pm 0.00
Eosinophils (%)	1.00 \pm 0.00	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Basophils(%)	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.33	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.61

P>0.05

Key: RBC; Red blood cells; WBC; White blood cells; Hb; Hemoglobin; PCV; Packed cell volume

method as described by (Adeyemo *et al.*, 2012)., Red blood cell (RBC) count was determined by the hemocytometer as described by Coles (1986) and Adeyemo *et al.* (2014) and total differential white blood cells (WBC) count using the improved Neubaur counting chamber as described by Coles (1986);Campbell *et al.* (2012) and Adeyemo *et al.* (2014).

Statistical Analysis

The data collected from phytochemical analysis, proximate analysis, safety of the extract hemagglutination test and hematological parameters, were recorded and tabulated as well as analyzed using descriptive statistic and presented in forms of tables. Hematological parameters were calculated into Mean and standard error means and presented in tables. The parameters were further subjected to Repeated Measure Anova statistical analysis using SPSS 29.0 version. $p < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

Phytochemical constituents of Ethanol Bark Extract of *Sweitenia macrophylla*

Analysis of phytochemical constituents of ethanol bark extract of *Sweitenia macrophylla* revealed the presence of metabolites (alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, glycoside, cardiac glycoside, terpenes, steroids and phenols).

Safety of *Sweitenia macrophylla* in the experimental Cockerels

The safety of the extract was evaluated and it was found to be safe at highest dose given (5500mg/kg body weight/day).

Antibody titer of the Cockerels

The result of hemagglutination test for the experimental

birds (groups C, D and E) before the experiment revealed each group had antibody titre of 1:20 (unprotective antibody titre for Newcastle disease).

Hematological parameters within the groups

In the negative control group (A), the mean cumulative parameters showed no statistically significant difference within the group ($p > 0.05$) from days 1, 3, 5 and 7 post infection in each of the parameters: Packed Cell Volume (PCV), Hemoglobin concentration (Hb), red blood cell (RBC), white blood cell (WBC), Heterophils, Lymphocytes, Monocytes, Eosinophils and Basophils (Table 1).

In positive control group (B), there was gradual increase in PCV and RBC from day 3 to day7 (Table 2). There was slight increase in lymphocytes and slight decrease in monocytes and eosinophils. The mean cumulative parameters showed no statistically significant difference within the group ($p > 0.05$) between days 1, 3, 5 and 7 post infection in each of the parameters: PCV, Hb, RBC, WBC, Heterophils, Lymphocytes, Monocytes, Eosinophils and Basophils.

For the second positive control group (C), there was gradual decrease in PCV, RBC and Hb, from day 3 to day 7 post infection. At day 7, PCV was below normal range. RBC and Hb were below normal range at days 5 and 7. There was increase in Lymphocytes above normal range in all the days but there was no statistically significant difference between the days ($p > 0.05$). Heterophils were slightly above normal range. Total WBC, Monocytes and Eosinophils were within normal range. The mean cumulative parameters showed statistical significant difference within the group ($p < 0.05$) between days 1 to 7 in the following parameters: PCV, Hb, RBC, and WBC but there was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in Heterophils, Lymphocytes, Monocytes, Eosinophils and Basophils (Table 3).

In the treatment group (D), there was gradual decrease in PCV, RBC and Hb, from day 3 to day 7 post infection. They were below normal range at days 5 and 7. There was gradual increase in WBC but within normal range

Table 2: Mean and Standard error mean (\pm SEM) of hematological parameters of group B cockerels at day 1, 3, 5, and 7

Hematological parameters	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
PCV (%)	28.50 \pm 0.17	27.80 \pm 0.63	28.60 \pm 0.58	29.00 \pm 0.37
Hb (g/dl)	9.40 \pm 0.52	7.78 \pm 0.38	8.73 \pm 0.12	8.50 \pm 0.34
RBCx10 ⁵ cells/ mm ³	3.00 \pm 0.18	2.40 \pm 0.62	2.83 \pm 0.72	2.95 \pm 0.68
WBCx10 ³ cells/mm ³	17.07 \pm 0.12	16.57 \pm 0.39	17.50 \pm 0.68	17.70 \pm 0.14
Heterophils(%)	36.00 \pm 0.18	36.00 \pm 0.13	37.00 \pm 0.71	37.00 \pm 0.62
Lymphocytes (%)	62.00 \pm 0.81	62.00 \pm 0.31	61.00 \pm 0.62	62.00 \pm 0.64
Monocytes(%)	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Eosinophils(%)	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Basophils(%)	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00

Key: RBC; Red blood cell; WBC; White Blood Cells; Hb; Hemoglobin; PCV; Parked Cell Volume.

Table 3: Mean and Standard error mean (\pm SEM) of hematological parameters of group C cockerels at day 1, 3, 5 and 7

Haematological parameters	Day 1	Day 3	Day5	Day 7
PCV(%)	28.20 \pm 0.66	25.60 \pm 0.19	20.75 \pm 0.81	19.50 \pm 1.31
Hb(g/dl)	8.80 \pm 0.21	7.30 \pm 0.83	6.15 \pm 0.91	5.10 \pm 1.78
RBCx10 ⁶ cells/mm ³	2.85 \pm 0.35	2.61 \pm 0.53	2.20 \pm 0.70	2.00 \pm 0.89
WBCx10 ³ cells/mm ³	11.10 \pm 0.56	19.29 \pm 0.38	20.10 \pm 0.89	22.23 \pm 0.95
Heterophils(%)	18.00 \pm 0.12	18.00 \pm 0.23	18.50 \pm 0.16	19.00 \pm 1.23
Lymphocytes(%)	76.00 \pm 0.21	77.00 \pm 0.26	77.66 \pm 0.51	77.00 \pm 1.56
Monocytes(%)	2.00 \pm 0.18	2.00 \pm 0.32	2.00 \pm 0.89	2.00 \pm 0.71
Eosinophils(%)	3.00 \pm 0.58	3.00 \pm 0.50	3.00 \pm 0.31	2.00 \pm 0.72
Basophils (%)	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00

Key: RBC; Red blood cell; WBC; White Blood Cells; Hb; Hemoglobin; PCV; Parked Cell Volume.

Table 4: Mean and Standard error mean (\pm SEM) of hematological parameters of group C cockerels at day 1, 3, 5 and 7

Haematological Parameters	Day 0	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
PCV(%)	28.20 \pm 0.64	24.90 \pm 0.21	20.5 \pm 0.85	19.10 \pm 0.87
Hb(g/dl)	8.50 \pm 0.23	7.10 \pm 0.43	6.00 \pm 0.36	5.50 \pm 0.11
RBCx10 ⁶ cells/mm	2.95 \pm 0.76	2.50 \pm 0.25	2.02 \pm 0.32	1.95 \pm 0.82
WBCx10 ³ cells/mm	12.01 \pm 0.23	15.50 \pm 0.38	19.61 \pm 0.45	21.10 \pm 0.56
Heterophils(%)	20.33 \pm 0.24	20.85 \pm 0.62	21.67 \pm 0.81	21.60 \pm 0.32
Lymphocytes(%)	74.00 \pm 0.30	75.00 \pm 0.43	77.00 \pm 0.20	77.00 \pm 0.65
Monocytes(%)	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Eosinophils(%)	3.00 \pm 0.00	3.00 \pm 0.00	3.00 \pm 0.50	2.00 \pm 0.10
Basophils (%)	0.00 \pm 0.67	0.00 \pm 0.15	0.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.40

Key: RBC; Red blood cell; WBC; White Blood Cells; Hb; Hemoglobin; PCV; Parked Cell Volume

and gradual increase in Lymphocytes above normal range. Monocytes slight decreased below normal range and there increase in Eosinophils slightly above normal range. The mean cumulative parameters showed a statistically significant difference within the group ($p < 0.05$) from day 1, 3, 5 and 7 post infection in the following parameters: PCV, Hb, RBC, WBC, and Eosinophils, but there was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in Lymphocytes, Heterophils and Monocytes (Table 4).

In the prophylactic group (E), there was gradual decrease in PCV (within normal range), gradual decrease in Hb and RBC also within normal range except for day 7 where both were below normal range. The mean cumulative parameters showed a statistically significant difference within the group ($p < 0.05$) from day 1, 3, 5 and

7 post infection in Heterophils and Lymphocytes. Lymphocytes were highest on day 1 and lowest on day 7. There was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the remaining parameters (Table 5).

Mean hematological values between the groups

Comparison between the groups showed highest PCV in group B and lowest in D. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups except for D with B and they were all within normal range. For Hemoglobin (Hb), group A had highest value while group D had lowest. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups and they were all within normal range. For the red blood cells (RBCs), the highest values were recorded in groups A and B and lowest in

Table 5: Mean and Standard error mean (\pm SEM) of hematological parameters of group E cockerels at day 1, 3, 5 and 7.

Haematological parameters	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
PCV(%)	28.50 \pm 0.30	27.50 \pm 0.42	26.00 \pm 0.62	25.34 \pm 0.13
Hb(g/dl)	8.87 \pm 0.23	8.17 \pm 0.41	8.53 \pm 0.52	8.24 \pm 0.26
RBCx10 ⁶ cells	2.51 \pm 0.21	2.77 \pm 0.10	2.66 \pm 0.41	2.42 \pm 0.10
WBCx10 ³	16.77 \pm 0.32	18.02 \pm 0.12	16.53 \pm 0.19	15.22 \pm 0.23
Heterophils (%)	24.20 \pm 0.12	27.67 \pm 0.41	35.33 \pm 0.61	35.81 \pm 0.20
Lymphocytes(%)	71.67 \pm 0.23	71.10 \pm 0.54	62.75 \pm 0.10	60.54 \pm 0.67
Monocytes (%)	2.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Eosinophils (%)	3.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
Basophils (%)	0.00 \pm 0.13	0.00 \pm 0.33	0.00 \pm 0.20	1.00 \pm 0.65

Key: RBC; Red blood cell; WBC; White Blood Cells; Hb; Hemoglobin; PCV; Parked Cell Volume

Figure 1. Mean of the hematological parameters in all the groups

Key: PCV: Parked cell volume; RBC: Red blood cells; WBC: White blood cells

group D, there was no statistically significant difference in all the groups ($p > 0.05$) and they were all within normal range. The values for white blood cells (WBC) were highest in group C and lowest in group A there was no significant difference statistically between the groups ($p > 0.05$) and were within normal range. Heterophils were highest in group B and lowest in group C which had statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$), the values were within normal range. For Lymphocytes, they were highest in group C and lowest in group B, they were above normal range and there was no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) among the groups. For Monocytes, Eosinophils and Basophils, there were no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between all the groups. Values were within normal range. Comparison between the groups is presented in Figure 1.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the effects of ethanol bark extract of Mahogany (*Sweetenia macrophylla*) on hematological parameters of cockerels experimentally infected with Kudu 113 velogenic strain of Newcastle disease virus.

The tree *S. macrophylla* occupies significant place in African, Asian, and South African countries. *S. macrophylla* has been traditionally found to be of medicinal use in treatment of many illnesses in humans and animals (Goh and Kadir, 2011).

The plant *S. macrophylla* is a potential blood purifier by having a high quantity of saponin which possesses anticoagulant, anticarcinogenic, antiviral, antitumor, antioxidative and hepatoprotective properties (Yadav and Agarwala, 2011). Tannins contained in *S. macrophylla*

have the ability to capture free radicals and form complexes with metal ions (Deng *et al.*, 2019). Flavonoids one of the components of *S. macrophylla* bark extract are known to improve vascular function and lowers blood pressure (Ciumărnean *et al.*, 2020). Terpenophenolic compounds which are also contained in the extract have been revealed to alleviate cardiovascular-related complications such as high blood pressure and atherosclerosis (Abdul-Ghani *et al.*, 2023).

White blood cells are cells of the immune system involved in defending the body against both infectious diseases and foreign materials (Roberts, 2012). Five types exist and occur throughout the body where they may be found in tissues, blood and in the lymphatic system. Increase in number of WBCs in the blood is often an indicator of disease (Travares-Dias *et al.*, 2008).

In the negative control group (A), the mean cumulative parameters showed no statistically significant difference within the group ($p > 0.05$) from days 1, 3, 5 to 7 post infection in each of the parameters. In positive control group (B), there was gradual increase in PCV from day 3-7 which were within normal range (Table 2). This could be attributed to the effect of the extract on these parameters. The increase in Lymphocytes and slight decrease in Monocytes and Eosinophils within the groups was not significant statistically.

For Positive control group (C) which were infected with the vNDV without intervention, there was gradual decrease in PCV, RBC and Hb, from day 3 to day 7 post infection. At day 7, PCV was below normal range, also RBC and Hb were below normal range on days 5 and 7. This could be due to effect of the virus on RBC (hemagglutination). There was gradual increase in Lymphocytes from day 1 to 5 all above normal range. Heterophils were slightly above normal range. Total WBC, Monocytes and Eosinophils were within normal range. This could be due to response to the virus by the immune system of the chickens.

In the therapeutic treatment group (D), there was gradual decrease in PCV, RBC and Hb, from day 3 to day 7 post infection. They were below normal range at days 5 and 7 though not statistically significant. This could be due to effect of the virus on RBC (hemagglutination). There was gradual increase in WBC but within normal range and gradual increase in Lymphocytes above normal range. This is also attributed to response to the virus by the immune system of the chickens. Monocytes slight decreased below normal range and there was increase in Eosinophils slightly above normal range.

In the prophylactic treatment group (E), there was gradual decrease in PCV (within normal range), gradual decrease in Hb and RBC (from day 3 for RBC) also within normal range except for day 7 where both were below normal range. The PCV was below normal range only on day 7 in group C and PCV, Hb and RBC were below normal range at day 5 in group D. It is different in this

group compared to groups C and D where they were below normal range right from day 5. This shows that there was effect of the extract on the virus given before the experimental infection which eventually led to maintaining the levels of these parameters. There was increase in white blood cells which was not significant statistically ($p > 0.05$) lymphocytes had increased without statistically significant difference between the days ($p > 0.05$).

Malik (2018) reported NDV to cause statistically significant difference in the values of Hb, Heterophils, Lymphocytes, Monocytes and Eosinophils between infected and non-infected broiler chickens. Asaniyan and Olabisi (2021) disclosed aqueous extracts of dried Roselle plant (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) calyx to maintain haematological content of blood of broilers, which is contrary to our findings possibly because the chickens used were not infected as in this study where there were alterations in the parameters.

The study by Tolba *et al.* (2022) is related to findings of this work where they recommended the use of *Moringa Olifera* extract from the first day of rearing in Hubbard chicken with ND vaccination program as a prophylactic treatment in protection of birds against ND infection. This is because total and differential cell numbers increased in extract treated group and vaccinated against NDV much more than treated and unvaccinated group.

Ampitan *et al.*, (2023) reported that methanol extract of *Momordica balsamina* l at 2.5g/100 litres of water has very good curative abilities on Avian paramyxovirus-1 infection in broilers which recorded higher white blood cell activity with a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) association while the same fruit at 5.0g/100litres of water had the best results for prophylactic treatments recording highest white blood cell count which was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). They recommended the use of *Mormodica balsamina* between 2.5g/100litres and 5g/100liters of water for the control and prevention of Newcastle disease. This is similar to the findings of this work.

Omeke *et al.* (2023) reported that prophylactic treatment of broiler chickens challenged with vNDV with methanol leaf extract of *Anacardium occidentale* at 300, 150, and 75 mg/kg and therapeutic treatment at 300 mg/kg led to significant ($p < 0.05$) higher white blood cell count but prophylactic treatment at 300 mg/kg, led to significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowering of the erythrocytic profile. This is in line with the findings of this work where higher white blood cell count was observed in therapeutic treatment group than in prophylactic treatment group.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that administration of *Sweitenia macrophylla* ethanol bark extract administration for prophylactic and therapeutic treatments at 3000mg/kg

enhanced white blood cells production in cockerels experimentally infected with velogenic Newcastle disease virus in this study. There was decrease in PCV, RBC and Hemoglobin in all the experimentally infected groups and PCV, Hb and Heterophils were highest in the prophylaxis treatment group compared to other infected groups.

RECOMMENDATION

The extract is recommended for prophylactic administration against Newcastle disease at 3000-5500mg/kg.

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